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Tidal and wave energy use cases to inform and engage stakeholders on potential effects on the environment and existing human uses

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Abstract

Offshore wind development off the U.S. Atlantic coast is moving forward but there has been little overall focus on the acceptability of the Atlantic region for marine energy. There is a need for regulators, marine energy device and project developers, local leaders, communities, and the general public to better understand the state of the knowledge regarding potential effects on the environment and existing human uses introduced by marine energy. Engaged communities are better able to separate perceived risks from actual risks, distinguish issues specific to marine energy from those of offshore wind development, and participate in decision-making processes. There is a growing body of knowledge world-wide that can inform the development of marine energy in the Atlantic region, but it must be made accessible and relatable.

In the context of the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), researchers from Pacific Northwest National Laboratory and the North Carolina Coastal Studies Institute have developed a focused outreach and engagement process around the science of what we know about environmental and social effects of marine energy development, as they pertain to project permitting and development. Use cases of potential environmental and social effects of marine energy projects were developed in two regions of the AMEC area: a tidal energy use case in southern New England, and a wave energy use case in North Carolina. These use cases were based on planned or typical projects and are not representative of any real-world project. Using existing data, specifics of potential deployment sites in each area were characterized and the animals and habitats potentially at risk examined. Other human uses of the area were also identified, including fishing, recreation, other offshore energy sites, etc. An assessment of the likely issues of concern was described for each use case, as they may affect permitting and licensing of marine energy projects. The use cases will be leveraged during workshops with stakeholders in the AMEC area to help illustrate the state of knowledge around environmental and social effects and benefits. The workshops will be held to discuss marine energy development with an emphasis on tidal energy in the northern area of AMEC (i.e., from Connecticut to New Hampshire) and wave energy in the southern area (i.e., North Carolina). The tidal energy workshop is planned in New Hampshire around the UMERC conference in October 2023 and the wave energy workshop will be held on the Outer Banks in North Carolina during the winter of 2024.

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1. Introduction

Marine energy is defined as the energy harvested from the movement of water in the oceans or large rivers (i.e., waves, tides, ocean currents, and river flows) and from ocean gradients (i.e., temperature and salinity gradients). Offshore wind is excluded because the source of power is not ocean water. While at a much slower scale than offshore wind projects, marine energy project deployments are increasing around the world and there is a need to monitor for potential effects on the marine environment as well as to understand environmental and social concerns expressed by the local communities. This is particularly true on the U.S. Atlantic coast where offshore wind is developing fast and marine energy lags behind, remaining relatively unknown in the eyes of the public.

The environmental and social concerns of local communities and stakeholders has led to local opposition to marine energy project deployments in certain circumstances, and more broadly, can indicate a lack of social acceptability of these projects. Social acceptability of marine energy projects includes community acceptance, which refers to the responses of local stakeholders, and it is an attitudinal construct [1]. It is based on attitudes, which arise from a range of factors, including perceptions of the project's effects and place-based values [2]. Attitude formation does not require knowledge or information about marine energy technologies [3]. Increasing knowledge does not automatically lead to improved attitudes and acceptability, but dissemination of relevant and accessible information in context-appropriate ways is a core element of engagement processes that center stakeholder and community needs and values in efforts to garner greater acceptability [4].

The Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC) is a university-led consortium created to address the ongoing needs for research, development, and testing on the Atlantic coast to advance utility-scale marine energy technologies towards commercialization, and to develop smaller-scale off-grid applications. To support AMEC's effort, researchers from Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) and the North Carolina Coastal Studies Institute (NCCSI) have developed a focused outreach and engagement process around the science of what we know about environmental and social effects of marine energy development, as they pertain to project permitting and development. The project team is conducting in-person stakeholder workshops to specifically deliver the state of knowledge regarding potential environmental and social effects of marine energy in New Hampshire, focused on tidal energy, and in North Carolina, focused on wave energy.

The workshops will focus on environmental and social issues specific to marine energy deployments and how those differ from what stakeholders may be more familiar with around offshore wind development happening in the region, as well as development of other energy projects. The review of past and present marine energy activities on the U.S. Atlantic coast, as well as PNNL's long-standing experience with environmental effects of marine energy (e.g., see state of the science reviews in [5,6]) and NCCSI's ongoing research and engagement efforts around environmental and social aspects of marine energy, will help identify the main issues to discuss at the workshops.

2. The workshops

A series of workshops have been developed and will be delivered, based on knowledge of the AMEC area from existing data and articulated around two use cases created specifically for engaging the audience on environmental and social effects of marine energy. To make the content of the in-person regional workshops more relatable to the participants, the team will describe use cases based on proposed projects or hypothetical but plausible examples. Stakeholder workshops will be directed towards regulatory agency staff and local communities. The participants will have the opportunity to engage with experts on potential effects of tidal and wave energy projects. The interactive workshops will allow the project team to engage with and answer questions and concerns by local stakeholders, as well as to understand local values that ought to influence the development of marine energy in their area.

The primary stakeholders invited to the workshops were identified through AMEC's network, as well as those who have expressed an interest in past and present marine energy activities on the U.S. Atlantic coast. Stakeholders include regulators, scientific advisors, tribal members, fishers, recreation and tourism industry participants, ports and shipping personnel, marine science researchers, and others. The two geographic locations (New Hampshire and North Carolina) will be represented by different groups of stakeholders who epitomize the important industries and communities in each area.

The workshop participants will gain a better understanding of the state of knowledge around potential environmental and social effects of marine energy development. Alongside additional engagement efforts and opportunities to participate in decision-making processes, greater understanding can translate to better acceptance and a sense of stewardship for marine energy projects in their respective regions, and perhaps bring some stakeholders around to being strong supporters. Addressing regulators and their science advisors may help inform and facilitate regulatory processes by creating better informed parties who will interact with marine energy developers around permitting discussions.

The success of the workshops will be measured in the short term by the presence and engagement with stakeholders at the events, and follow-up engagement afterwards, as needed. Two workshops will be held in each location (New Hampshire and North Carolina), one that is placed and timed to draw regulators and their advisors (mid-week, near the state capital) and one placed and timed for the convenience of the local coastal community (weekend, on the coast). In addition, the project team will provide the workshop attendees with paper copies of outreach material on environmental effects of marine energy as well as links to online material.

3. The use cases

Two use cases that demonstrate potential environmental and social effects of marine energy development were developed in the northern and southern regions of the AMEC area, in two specific locations that are potential targets for marine energy development. Developing the use cases helped the project team better understand the marine energy landscape on the U.S. Atlantic coast and prepare targeted outreach materials to engage with the stakeholders. The use cases will be leveraged during the in-person workshops to provide context and information on the current state of the science of marine energy environmental and social effects, and how the scientific community can address issues raised by stakeholders during the lifetime of a project.

To create the use cases, the team reviewed all past and present marine energy deployments and planned projects from Maine to Florida, identified the stakeholders involved, and listed all the environmental and user/stakeholder issues that have been raised during the planning and permitting processes. Based on this review, the team identified:

- A tidal energy use case in the northern region and a wave energy use case in the southern region (a use case for ocean current project may be added in the southern region);
- The diversity of users/stakeholders involved throughout a project (e.g., regulators, advisors, tribes, fishers, recreation and tourism industry, ports and shipping sector, marine science researchers, etc.) and issues that each group has raised; and
- The diversity of environmental and social issues that present similarities and differences with those related to offshore wind projects.

By leveraging knowledge gained from previous experiences, these use cases describe hypothetical marine energy projects and the environmental and social effects that might be expected to be raised around them. Based on this knowledge, specifics of each use case site were characterized and the animals and habitats potentially at risk examined. Other uses of the area were assessed, including fishing, recreation, other offshore energy sites, etc. An assessment of the likely issues of concern in each area was conducted for each use case, as they may affect permitting and licensing of marine energy projects.

The first use case to be developed was the New England tidal energy use case, located in the Muskeget Channel south of Cape Cod, MA. This use case is hypothetical and not descriptive of a marine energy project currently being proposed for the Muskeget Channel. However, it was inspired by proposed marine energy projects in the Muskeget Channel and other locations in New England, and includes knowledge gained from these previous experiences on site characteristics, potential environmental effects, and stakeholder involvement. The document (Fig. 1) starts with a description of the hypothetical tidal project, detailing the area, the technology, and the project's lifecycle. The next section covers the receptors of potential concern, such as fish, marine mammals, sea turtles, and benthic habitats. The following section details the potential interactions between the project's tidal turbines and the surrounding marine environment. The last section provides a list of local, regional, and federal stakeholders that would be involved during the lifetime of the project and the potential concerns they may raise.

4. Conclusion

The tidal energy use case will be presented and leveraged during the first series of in-person workshops, which will be held on two days around the UMERC conference, the first week of October 2023 in New Hampshire, focused

on marine energy development with an emphasis on tidal energy in the northern area of AMEC (i.e., from Connecticut to New Hampshire). The first edition of the workshop will occur on the weekday preceding UMERC's start and will be held at a location convenient to the state capital and the university campus, to attract agency staff, academic researchers, and others. The second workshop will occur on the Saturday following UMERC and will be held on the coast (likely Portsmouth) to engage with local community, fishers, and others.

With these workshops, the project team hopes to engage with a wide spectrum of stakeholders from the U.S. Atlantic coast that may be the most suitable for tidal and wave energy development, increase their awareness of marine energy and its potential environmental and social effects, with the aim of improving local knowledge of marine energy and create support for this developing industry.

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Fig. 1. Outline of the tidal energy project use case in New England.

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